

1 Density Analysis

The distribution of interrogative comments per PR for human-generated vs the normalized RCG-generated reviews.

(a) All Comments

(b) Discussion-inducing Comments

Figure 1: Distribution of interrogative comments per PR for human-generated vs. normalized RCG-generated reviews for (a) all the comments (b) discussion-inducing comments.

The entropy of the interrogative comments.

Figure 2: The entropy of the interrogative comments for each studied RCG over different values of top-k for all comments (left) and discussion-inducing comments (right).

The p-values for the Mann-Whitney-U test.

p-value trend across top-k values

Figure 3: The p-values for the Mann-Whitney-U test for all comments (left) and discussion-inducing comments (right).

2 Frequency Analysis

The trend of changes in the interrogative ratio in different settings.

Figure 4: Change of interrogative comments ratio (%) for all the studied RCGs.

The odds ratios and Fisher’s exact text p-values for the studied RCGs.

Figure 5: The odds ratios and Fisher’s exact text p-values for the studied RCGs.